

Traditional Game-Based Learning: as a Local Wisdom Learning Model in Elementary School

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received October 05, 2020</p> <p>Accepted December 19, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Traditional Game-Based Learning, Local wisdom, values, social studies, elementary school</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4362259</p>	<p><i>A fun and meaningful learning process at school is an important component in fostering student motivation and developing student affective aspects. This research will reveal how traditional game-based learning in social studies learning in elementary schools today. Traditional games are part of local wisdom. Traditional games have local character values which are very important for students in facing the challenges of the 21st century. Through traditional game-based social studies learning, students can find out about their disappearing culture and can preserve and internalize the values contained in everyday life. Therefore, this study embodies and implements traditional game-based learning. This research data collection techniques through questionnaires, interviews, and technical observation of data analysis using qualitative and quantitative analysis. The results showed that the absence of a Traditional Game Based Learning model in social studies learning and social studies learning based on values of traditional games is still relevant and needs to be implemented in 21st century learning</i></p>

I. INTRODUCTION

Traditional children's games are games that are passed down from generation to generation that are used as a means of learning and socializing children [1]. In fact now, traditional games are starting to be forgotten, many children do not know some of the traditional games of their own region. Traditional games are a part of the childhood of our nearly extinct ancestors, some generations of parents still remember them, but knowledge of traditional games in children in modern society is very low [2]. Lack of understanding and knowledge of traditional games is due to the fact that most children's play activities are dominated by digital media and reduced playing space in cities and villages [3], so that children lose the experience of playing and interacting with their peers. Digital-based games cannot create social interactions like traditional games [4]. Educated in the digital world, millennial children lack social interactions and direct activities involving fine and gross motor skills [5].

The results of previous research revealed that through the values of traditional games it can promote culture, interact with others, utilize natural resources, develop self-characteristics and develop psychomotor. [6]. Playing traditional games has a functional role in pediatric patient care, can reduce stress and anxiety, accelerate recovery and rehabilitation, facilitate communication, act as an outlet to express feelings, help children regain their confidence and self-esteem, help pediatric patients hospitalization or surgery [7]. Medical-related research is continued [8], the aim of this study is to explore how traditional games are used as a strategy to prevent HIV in Zambia. Traditional play provides benefits through the character values implied in it. Children can realize the importance of cultural preservation as a national identity. [9] fosters a sense of unity and democracy as well as reflective skills among students [10], develops children's creativity, because most play tools are made by themselves [11].

Traditional games can be integrated in learning. The constructivist approach explains the importance of game-based learning in the classroom [12]. In line with [13] research, the game model has been successfully applied in the field of social science with interactions in it. through a game model, it can solve real-life problems related to misunderstanding and disputed behavior. Children and adults can learn and develop through play, there is a reason behind integrating games into teaching strategies to create active learning and improve students' critical thinking skills [14]. The ability to think critically is one of the 21st century skills that students must have. At this time the focus of educational institutions is helping students acquire 21st century skills, one of which is helping children develop complex problem solving skills [15]. Traditional games are flexible and practical so they are very effective in being used as a medium in the teaching and learning process. Traditional games are seen as simple and low cost (Njelesani & Njelesani, 2019). In Indonesia, the game has been implemented by teachers in schools even though it is still not systematic [16]. Traditional games that are applied in schools, create conditions that require students to follow activities in the field [17].

The integration of traditional games in social studies learning is intended to provide understanding and understanding of local culture in particular so that students are expected to develop character values. Traditional games that are full of noble values and moral messages as a filter against the negative impacts of globalization. [18] states that traditional games can be presented in learning through the ethnopedagogical method. It can explore the potential for modeling cultural constructs such as traditional games as a means of health communication and a behavior change agent [19]. Fun learning based on traditional games which is full of values with the hope that in the future, these values can be internalized in their daily lives so that they can face and solve life's problems.

Based on the above background, it is necessary to conduct an in-depth study of how the objective conditions of social studies learning that have been implemented in elementary schools then identify the conditions of social studies learning based on traditional games that are currently taking place in relation to character development through social studies learning based on local traditions in the form of traditional games.

II. METHODS

Observations or field studies were carried out by researchers to get clarity in the field regarding traditional game-based learning that touches the affective, cognitive and psychomotor development of students in elementary schools. Observation is used by researchers as the basis for making traditional game-based learning models apart from referring to previous research and literature studies from related books. The observation phase or field study is realized by distributing questionnaires via the internet Google Form which can be accessed via the internet network. Google Forms is a cloud-based data management tool used to design and develop web-based questionnaires. This tool is provided by Google Inc, and is available on the web for anyone to use and create a web-based questionnaire. Anywhere, anytime access, and other benefits of unlimited, free surveys have made Google Forms a popular product in online survey research [20].

The purpose of distributing questionnaires in this study was to obtain an overview of traditional game-based learning that has been implemented in elementary schools. The questionnaires were distributed to 56 elementary school teachers in Bandung City. To complete and obtain complete and more in-depth information, in addition to distributing questionnaires, researchers conducted in-depth interviews related to respondents' views and understanding of traditional game-based learning to 5 teachers.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The preparation stage in conducting this research was a needs analysis which consisted of field observations, interviews, and questionnaires. The observation activity aims to determine the state of the learning process, starting from the activities of the learning actors, the learning situation both in class or outside the classroom, and learning facilities. In-depth interview activities are aimed at classroom teachers and some students to find out more information about the conditions and needs of students in learning traditional game-based social studies in schools. The activity of distributing questionnaires to teachers and students to find out the conditions and needs of students in learning.

The needs analysis raises several criteria into consideration that the product of the Traditional Game-Based Learning model that will be developed in research is important for education, especially in character education based on local wisdom values, with the aim of creating a golden generation of 2045 who has a personality in a culture that is pious, nationalist, resilient, independent, and has the advantage to compete globally.

The initial stage of needs analysis was made a questionnaire for classroom teachers in Bandung City to get clarity about Traditional Game Based Learning in elementary schools at this time which is important for cultivating the cultural character of students. Distribution of questionnaires using the Google Form feature that can be accessed via the internet with the topic "Traditional Game Based Learning". The use of the Google Form feature makes it easier for respondents to access it anywhere and anytime via their cellphone, android or computer device. Based on the results of observations at the needs analysis stage, there were 56 respondents who participated in this observation.

From the observations found, almost all respondents know and have analyzed material related to traditional games in social studies lessons in elementary schools as evidenced by the results of the questionnaire as follows the questionnaire distributed to classroom teachers, it can be found that 89.3% of respondents who include

elementary school teachers from some class levels do not know or find the Traditional Game Based Learning (TGBL) learning model. In terms of knowledge about traditional games, 85.7% of respondents said that in the social studies lesson content in SD, there are basic competencies that must be achieved by students in relation to culture-based learning, which implies traditional game-based learning. Furthermore, several respondents said they had done this

Traditional game-based learning is limited to students doing some traditional games, but not yet at the evaluation and reflection stages. With respect to TGBL, 98.2% of respondents agreed that social studies learning based on traditional game values is still relevant and needs to be implemented in the 21st century.

The results of the preliminary study show that the learning process related to local wisdom-based material has not illustrated any efforts to improve the affective domain related to the values of local wisdom characters, especially the values implied in traditional games. Teaching materials have not strengthened the inculcation of the character values of local wisdom, especially in teaching materials about traditional games. Meanwhile, the results of studying the available primary school curriculum can be developed into material characterized by local wisdom.

The characteristics of the learning process in elementary schools are adjusted to the characteristics of competencies and are fully directed at developing these three domains holistically, meaning that the development of one domain cannot be separated from another. So that the learning process as a whole gives birth to personal qualities with attitudes, knowledge and skills.

Play activities and students are an inseparable unit, both have a very close relationship, playing is one way students learn [23], expressing the results of thoughts through the surrounding environment, so that students will find various experiences and developmentally elementary school students are at the stage of playing with simple rules, one of which is playing traditional games [24]. Game-based learning is used to create enjoyable experiences and motivate student learning so as to create meaningful learning experiences through values in games and can be applied in the real world [25].

Game-based constructivist learning has received great attention as educational institutions aim to shift from traditional instructional teaching to interactive and collaborative methods [26]. Interactive and collaborative methods are a means of developing affective, cognitive and psychomotor learners. Affective, cognitive and psychomotor development of students cannot be separated from the help of those around students. Interaction with adults or with peers in the immediate environment can encourage children in their development process. A series of tasks or activities that are difficult for children to master or solve can be learned or solved with help from others such as teachers or friends who are more capable.

Learning conditions based on local wisdom (traditional games) which are loaded with the values contained today are very much needed as a way to preserve the nation's culture through education and as a filter against the negative impacts of globalization. The integration of traditional games in social studies learning is intended to provide understanding and understanding of local culture in particular so that students are expected to develop character values and 21st century skills. Traditional game-based learning explores the potential for modeling cultural constructs such as traditional games as a means of agents of behavior change [27]. The results of research by [28] state that schools that integrate character values with direct experience of the environment in the classroom give good results in terms of knowledge.

The teacher presents fun learning based on traditional games that are full of values with the hope that in the future these values can be internalized in their daily lives so that they can face and solve life's problems. Social studies learning must be able to create students with character, teaching materials that contain character values must be able to be internalized in social studies learning so that students are able to apply them in everyday life.

The Traditional Game Based Learning model is a cultural wisdom-based learning model which is expected to provide the basics of character education to students from an early age through the learning process. The traditional game-based learning process involves the subject matter of Social Sciences or the theme being implemented, the learning methods used, and classroom management. Using the traditional game-based learning model, the selection of learning methods can be used as a medium for developing character through learning activities. Value-based contextual learning in developing the character of students through the Traditional game-based learning model can be applied in teaching to develop the five main characters of students including religion, nationalism, mutual cooperation, integrity and independence. Five character values that are part of the government program in echoing character education are implied in the values of traditional games which consist of Relationship with God, Relationship with Self, Relationships with Others, Relationship with the Environment and Nationality values.

The values implied in traditional games serve as a medium for conveying cultural messages to the next generation. As a cultural activity, traditional games strengthen cultural values that can stimulate creativity, even a story expert stated that the essence of folk games includes elements of entertainment, fostering creativity and shaping personality. The five main character values that are implied in the values of traditional games in the learning process, especially in social studies subject content, can foster 21st century skills (creative, collaborative, critical thinking, communication) so that students are able to anticipate conditions of moral

degradation, ethics and character as an impact. negative from the era of globalization, and the goal is to think globally act locally.

Internalizing the values of traditional games through the learning process with the TGBL model is one way to achieve goals in developing character. If students have been able to internalize values into their souls (the process of reasoning, appreciation, and practice) then they are expected to make good and bad decisions, maintain what is good, and realize the good in everyday life wholeheartedly. In addition, students can have character and be able to face the challenges of life now and in the future, in the context of life in society, nation and state of Indonesia.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that the negative impact of globalization at this time greatly affects the attitudes and character of students. The Traditional Game-Based Learning model is a local wisdom learning model that acts as a means of preserving local wisdom that is starting to disappear and as a filter for the negative impacts of globalization. The values implied in traditional games serve as a medium for conveying cultural messages to the next generation. As a cultural activity, traditional games strengthen cultural values that can be instilled in students which are then internalized in everyday life., Five main character values implicit in the values of traditional games (Relationship with God, Relationship with Self, Relationships with Others, Relationship with the Environment and Nationality values) in the learning process, especially in social studies subject content, can foster 21st century skills (creative, collaborative, critical thinking, communication) so that students are able to anticipate conditions of moral degradation, ethics and character as a negative impact of globalization era, and the goal is think globally act locally.

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